

Glimpses of Victorious Women in Science

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Pereira, Tanya.

“Glimpses of Victorious
Women in Science.”

*Shanlax International
Journal of Arts, Science
and Humanities,*
vol. 6, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 139–42.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.2551386](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551386)

Abstract

Women are a minority in academic positions the world over, although the number of women receiving doctorates and in academic positions has increased over the last twenty years. Women still face gender-based discrimination and a lack of equal opportunities having to face a number of challenges, such as socio-cultural and gender discrimination, barriers to access and advancement, ostracism and psychological barriers. Only 51 women in total have been awarded the Nobel Prize between 1901 and 2018. This article highlights the stories of a few women in Natural Sciences who represent women in science who have accomplished commendable heights through unfavourable conditions and are symbols of inspiration to humanity – they have surpassed barriers of gender, social, financial or other challenges and have used their talents for the benefit of society and the world at large.

Keywords: women scientists, natural science, discoveries, gender discrimination.

Introduction

Women have made significant contributions to science from time immemorial. Women scientists have no doubt shaped science through the ages whether they have been acknowledged or not. The earliest records are from Ancient Egypt (2700 BC) of Merit-Ptah who was the medical practitioner at Pharaoh's court (Jahren, 2017). Texts in cuneiform tablets dating back to 1200 BC have records of the work of Mesopotamian Tapputi who is considered the world's first Chemist. She prepared tinctures and perfumes using plant extracts through distillation and this is the first record of the very first still. She made these natural extracts using oils, myrrh, flowers, and natural resins in aqueous and organic solvents. Tapputi had a very important place in the royal family as she was called “Belatekallim” which is the title given to the palace overseer (Levey, 1973; Sherdia, 1975). Since its institution in 1901, the Nobel Prize awardees have been predominantly men. In the category of Physiology or Medicine, only 12 women have received the Nobel Prize out of a total of 216 awardees over the last 117 years (Nobel Media AB, 2019). The article highlights a few examples of remarkable women who have overcome tremendous obstacles and achieved outstanding success in natural sciences.

Marie Curie (1867 -1934)

Nothing in life is to be feared, it is only to be understood.

Marie Curie known for her discovery of polonium and radium is one of the world's most inspirational scientists. She is a remarkable woman whose life is a testament to the changing role of women in science over the past century. Curie developed methods for the separation of radium from radioactive residues and examined its properties for its therapeutic potential. She shared the Nobel Prize for Physics in 1903 with her husband Pierre Curie, for research on the spontaneous radiation. In 1911, she received a second Nobel Prize in Chemistry, in recognition of her work in radioactivity. Throughout her life, Marie Curie worked on using radium to alleviate suffering during World War I. Marie Curie is known for her quiet, dignified, unassuming and meticulous ways. She is admired by scientists throughout the world as her discoveries paved way for novel approaches in physics and chemistry and lead to advances in engineering, biology, and medicine. Marie Curie was born in Poland but pursued her higher education in Paris because France permitted women into their universities. She was raised in a family that valued education for all people regardless of gender or class. Marie Curie also worked as a governess and tutored the less privileged. She made time for family and friends and did not allow her passion for science to impede upon her duties towards her family. Curie had a heart for people and worked not for her own glory but used her talents for the benefit of all in society. She made a deliberate decision to publish the data on the isolation and purification of radium, rather than pursuing patents on the process, although this allowed many companies to exploit the situation and with no financial benefits for themselves. She is an inspiration to all women in science being the first woman to win Nobel Prize, the first woman to lecture at the Sorbonne, the first person to win two Nobel Prizes, and the first Nobel Laureate whose daughter, Irene Curie, also won a Nobel Prize (Rockwell, 2003).

Barbara McClintock (1902-1992)

If you know you are on the right track, if you have this inner knowledge, then nobody can turn you off....no matter what they say.

Barbara McClintock is a lady with a passion for science. She won the Nobel Prize for the discovery of transposable elements in *Zea mays*. The transposable elements or jumping genes transformed the understanding of genetic patterns of inheritance. Barbara McClintock worked in the mid-twentieth century amidst numerous challenges in an androcentric scientific world. Her determination, quest for knowledge, and heart for nature, enabled her to become a Nobel laureate. She examined the structure and function of the chromosomes in corn cells and proposed mechanisms of how genes combined and how these interactions were regulated. She was the first to conceptualise that hereditary material was not static and may be subject to re-arrangement or alteration during the development of an organism. In 1910, Rollins Adams Emerson's had reported the occurrence of purple or brown spots on white kernels in maize, and hypothesized that the spots occurred due to unstable mutations on chromosomes but was not able to provide experimental evidence. McClintock was able to prove that the occurrence of unexpected purple- and brown-coloured kernels was due to genetic transposition. McClintock presented her findings at a Cold Spring Harbor Symposium in 1951. However the prejudiced audience at the conference considered her results to be obscure and difficult to understand because they went against the grain of the existing theories of genetic material being static. It was only three decades later, in 1983, that her work received recognition. She is the very first woman to be the sole recipient of the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine (Craig, 1994; Comfort, 2001).

Rachel Carson (1907-1964)

Those who contemplate the beauty of the earth find reserves of strength that will endure as long as life lasts.

Rachel Carson is a Biologist and a nature writer, best known for her book *Silent Spring*, in which she exposes the ill-effects of pesticides on the environment. She is one of the pioneer environmentalists to create awareness against pesticides. She was an outspoken advocate for the environment and a great social revolutionary questioning the relationship between people and nature, asking profound questions such as “Are human beings the dominant authority?” Carson advocated that DDT and other similar pesticides and insecticides should be referred to as biocides. She was firm in her views that they are anti-life, and that “herbicides” cannot restrict their toxicity to plants. Carson warned that a “whole chain of poisoning” was inevitable as DDT moves from water to plankton, to insect, to fish, to birds, to people. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) was founded in December 1970, largely in response to *Silent Spring* (Paull, 2007).

Frances Arnold (1956 -)

You have to believe in yourself. If you have a good idea, follow it, even when others say it is not.

The Nobel Prize in Chemistry 2018 was awarded to Frances H. Arnold, the fifth woman to receive the award in Chemistry. Her research is on directed evolution and phage displays, which speed up laboratory production of new kinds of bacteria-produced enzymes and peptides. Frances Arnold believed in her ideas that centred on the benefit of mankind. She had a clear vision: to benefit humanity through the development of new technology. Arnold was not afraid to change her course from solar power to DNA technology, in tune with the political shift in objectives after the 1981 presidential elections in the United States. She said, “Directed evolution allows me to rewrite the code of life and particularly to do it to solve human problems. I hope that women will see that one can have a rewarding career in science and technology” (Golgowski, 2018). The methods developed by 2018 Nobel Laureates in Chemistry have laid the foundation for a revolution in chemistry. Their techniques are developed are now being internationally developed to promote a greener chemicals industry, produce new materials, manufacture sustainable biofuels, mitigate autoimmune diseases and even metastatic cancer (Nobel Media AB 2019).

Donna Strickland (1959 -)

I see myself as a scientist, not a woman in science.

Donna Strickland is a Canadian Physicist and the third woman in history to win the Nobel Prize in Physics. She was honoured with the award in 2018 for a method of generating high-intensity, ultra-short optical pulses. Short pulse lasers have a myriad of applications beyond eye surgery, with ramifications throughout physics, biology, chemistry, materials science, industry and medicine. Matthias Kling, a laser physicist at Ludwig Maximilian University in Munich, Germany affirmed Strickland’s work saying, “Chirped pulse amplification is as important as the invention of the laser itself” (Moyer and Wolchover, 2018). Strickland’s fascination for lasers started at a tender age when she visited the Ontario Science Centre with her family. She is a person who acknowledges the gender disparity in Science, a true scientist at heart who truly enjoys working in Physics to the point where work is fun. She said that the green and red laser lights in her lab enkindled a spirit of Christmas in the lab (Valich, 2018).

Conclusion

Each of these women are shining examples to the scientific community and have demonstrated a deep commitment to science, overcome social discrimination including gender-bias with remarkable courage, determination, portrayed a willingness to fight for what is right despite the odds against them, and commitment to stand for truth for all humanity.

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